

(Grant Agreement 101093921)

T4.1 - Survey protocol to Identify enablers and barriers to co-design, co-develop and co-implement innovative solutions for climate resilience

HORIZON-MISS-2021-CLIMA-02-05 - Local engagement of citizens in the co-creation of societal transformational change for climate resilience

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Actions under grant agreement No 101093921

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Background

This survey has been elaborated to capture the key factors supporting or hindering adaptation practitioners experienced with engaging citizens and stakeholders in adaptation initiatives. The results of the survey could be used to identify priority areas for upscaling adaptation co-production processes. This survey can be conducted online, in printed form or in person during an interview.

This survey is divided into 4 main sections which aim to:

1. Guaranteeing the respondent's age of majority, answers confidentiality and their approval for the use of the information collected for research purposes using a consent form.
2. Setting the stage to collect experiences about the adaptation and co-production process. The respondent is asked to focus on one experience of adaptation co-production process for the entire survey. A series of closed questions aimed to gather information, first about the experience under study (location, type, objectives, sectors) and then about the collaborative process linked to the adaptation initiative described (role of the respondent, type of engagement, stakeholders' type in charge and involved in the process, objectives and outcomes achieved).
3. Assessing the enablers and barriers experienced during the implementation of this process. Likert scales are used to assess the importance that each type of lever and barrier played within the process. Then, a group of questions aimed to identify which factors influenced the different steps of a co-production process (stakeholder/citizen engagement, climate vulnerability assessment, solutions selection and design, implementation and monitoring) and to identify respondents' motivations and constraints encountered.
4. Gathering socio-demographic information enabling to monitor the inclusiveness and profiles of the respondents. It includes questions about age group, gender, education level, place of residence and sector of activity. The survey was anonymous

The content of the survey should be adapted to specific needs and projects.

Targeted stakeholders

The stakeholder categories that are considered relevant for responding to this survey are adaptation practitioners, i.e. all professionals in charge of implementing adaptation initiatives, and more particularly those involved in collaborative processes engaging stakeholders and citizens. They may therefore be adaptation project leaders, public authority officials and civil servants in charge of designing and implementing local adaptation policies or researchers involved in research projects implementing co-production processes for adaptation to climate change. Respondents should possess the expertise and have experience in these areas, which is why selecting the sample is very important.

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Survey Design and general considerations

In this section, the survey will be outlined with the different sections which should always include:

- 1- Title that references the survey, general purpose and engages the audience
- 2- Introduction to the survey, explaining potential respondents the framework under which it will be carried out, the length, how data will be used and whether any personal data will be collected.
- 3- Common definitions, as it may not be the case that all respondents have in mind the same elements that define one concept. In order to avoid any issues, it is relevant to outline what it is meant by each of the terms that will be used throughout the survey.
- 4- Data processing and consent, while this may be informed in the first part, it is important to include a disclaimer and to allow respondents to agree to the treatment of the data they will be providing. This will be especially relevant if any personal data is collected which may include emails or other contact information.
- 5- Survey questions
- 6- Enabling future links with respondents
- 7- Providing further information
- 8- Communication and dissemination strategies

AGORA survey to identify enablers and barriers to co-design, co-develop and co-implement innovative solutions for climate resilience

1- Title

How to engage people in climate change adaptation? Share your experience with us!

2- Introduction to the survey

Dear respondent,

As part of the AGORA project, the survey aims to identify the levers and barriers you experienced in the design or implementation of collaborative processes in climate change adaptation.

The data collected from this survey will form the groundwork for identifying key policy priorities to expand and bolster people's engagement in adaptation initiatives throughout Europe. The survey takes around 10-15 minutes.

If you have any questions, please contact Enora Bruley at enora.bruley@unige.ch

Sincerely,

AGORA team

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3- Common definitions

Before we start, we would like to provide some definitions to have a common understanding of certain terms used:

Stakeholder: All the actors who may be involved in the collaborative development of adaptation initiatives.

Adaptation initiatives: It covers various adaptation initiative types that aim to address the impacts of climate change, e.g. on ground, social, behavioural, financial, institutional, or infrastructural.

Collaborative process: A process that involves a plurality of stakeholders in at least one step of an adaptation initiative design or implementation. We assume that different types of collaborative processes exist ranging from stakeholder consultation to co-decision making.

4- Data processing and consent

Section 1: Consent

Adhering to General Data Protection Regulation, all survey responses are confidential. We collect specific identity details only to help understand the demographic we have reached. The data from this survey will be used for scientific

purposes within the AGORA project. The analysis of the survey data will be therefore anonymous and aggregated.

AGORA privacy policy link: <https://adaptationagora.eu/privacy-policy/>

#1 - I have read and understood the information provided above.

- I voluntarily consent to participate in this survey.

- I consent to the processing of my anonymous data for research purposes

- Yes
- No

#2 I confirm that I am 18 years or older:

- Yes
- No

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5- Questions

Section 2: Information on the adaptation initiative and associated collaborative process

Now we would like to focus on your experience on ONE adaptation collaborative process you were involved in, ideally the one you know the most about. For the following questions please refer to one experience.

#3 In which country(ies) was the adaptation initiative implemented?

#4 What type of adaptation initiative was it?

- Climate service
- On ground solution implementation (e.g. Nature-based solutions)
- Institutional/Policy
- Financial
- Technical/infrastructural Research/innovation
- Social/behavioral
- Other

#5 What was the main objective(s) of this adaptation initiative (choose max 3 options)?

- Adaptation/risk reduction plan or strategies
- Policies or instruments design
- Capacity building
- Knowledge production or sharing
- Implementation of climate adaptation measures
- Other

#6 What sector(s) does the adaptation initiative belong in (choose max 3 options)? *

- Tourism
- No specific sector
- Fisheries and aquaculture
- Disaster risk reduction
- Agriculture and forestry
- Land use planning
- Infrastructure (Buildings/transport)
- Business and industry
- Environment (Biodiversity)
- Water management
- Cultural/heritage
- Energy
- Health
- Other

#7 What was your role in the collaborative process?

- Advisor
- Facilitator
- Expert
- Funder

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- Organiser
- Participant
- Other

#8 In your perspective, what type of stakeholder engagement does the process belong in?

- Inform: To provide stakeholders with balanced and objective information to assist in understanding the problem, alternatives, opportunities, and/or solutions.
- Extract: To gain stakeholders' information, which might or might not be shared in subsequent forums.
- Consult: To obtain public feedback on analysis, alternatives, and/or decisions.
- Involve: To work directly with stakeholders throughout the process to ensure that their concerns are consistently understood and considered.
- Collaborate: To partner with stakeholders in each aspect of the decision, including the identification, selection and development of the preferred solution.
- Empower: To place the final decision-making in the hands of the stakeholders.

#9 Which stakeholder groups organized the collaborative process? *

- Academia and research
- Governments and decision makers
- Investors/economic actors
- Media
- Citizens
- Local communities
- Civil society representatives/NGOs
- Other

#10 Which stakeholder groups took part in the collaborative process?

- Academia and research
- Civil society representatives/NGOs
- Citizens
- Local communities
- Investors/economic actors
- Governments and decision makers
- Media
- Other

#11 How was the process mandated?

- Voluntary process
- Binding process (legal requirement)
- Other

#12 In your perspective to what extent did the collaborative process achieve its objectives ?

- I don't know (I'm not able to measure, too soon to tell)
- None of the objectives were achieved despite efforts
- Most of the objectives were not achieved
- Some or a few of the objectives were achieved
- Most of the objectives were achieved

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- All the objectives were achieved and even more

#13 To what extent did the collaborative adaptation process deliver the following outcomes?

Strongly disagree Disagree Agree Strongly agree I don't know

- Participants mutually learned from the process and from each other
- There was clear communication and continuous information sharing
- Mutual respect, trust and healthy work relationships between participants were present or developed during the process
- Participants partnerships and networks strengthened as a result of the process
- Participants co- defined the adaptation problem, vulnerabilities, objectives and solutions
- The diversity of participants involved was appropriate for the affected demographic
- Participants had an equal opportunity to participate in the decision-making process
- Participant capacity building occurred during the process
- The adaptation solution(s) developed align with local needs, context, expectations, and values

Section 3: Experienced levers and barriers to the implementation and progress of adaptation collaborative processes

Based on the scientific literature review, we identified internal and external levers and barriers affecting climate change adaptation collaborative processes. Here we want to understand which levers and barriers played a role in your selected process design and implementation.

#14 On a scale from 1 (none) to 5 (very important), what role did these external levers play in the collaborative process implementation?

- Stakeholder motivations (e.g. experience of climate impacts/risks, urgency)
- Financial support (e.g. reward structure, long- term funding)
- Intermediaries support (e.g. facilitators or experts' involvement)
- Existing social capital (e.g. networks, long lasting relations)
- Institutional support (e.g. government commitment, legal framework)
- Knowledge availability (e.g. knowledge accessibility, usability, saliency)
- Capacity to engage (e.g. incomes, education, awareness)

#15 On a scale from 1 (none) to 5 (very important), what role did these internal levers play in the collaborative process implementation?

- Building an inclusive approach (e.g. representativeness, inclusiveness (gender, social groups))
- Building an integrative approach (e.g. recognition of different values, contexts, world-views)
- Co defining participants role (e.g. power balance, equity, shared responsibilities)
- Relying on people (e.g. local champions, boundary organisation)
- Building relevant process (e.g. flexibility, system thinking)
- Building strong communication (e.g. dialogue space, transparency)

#16 On a scale from 1 (none) to 5 (very important), what role did these external barriers play in the collaborative process implementation?

- Institutional barriers (e.g. lack or constraining legal framework, inadequate funding scheme)

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- Inadequate organisation (e.g. siloed organisation, unsuitable governance system)
- Lack of engagement (e.g. overwhelmed actors, lack of time, cultural barriers)
- Lack of recognition (e.g. of actors' knowledge and needs)
- Lack of capabilities (e.g. socio-economic barriers, heavy bureaucracy)

#17 On a scale from 1 (none) to 5 (very important), what role did these internal barriers play in the collaborative process implementation?

- Inadequate internal coordination (e.g. lack of experience, miscommunication, late involvement)
- Power imbalance (e.g. gender issues, intra-group power, hidden power)
- Lack of resource (e.g. process sustainability, human resource)
- Conflicting interests (e.g. entrenched thinking, distinct motivations)
- Dealing with complexities (e.g. uncertainties, sophisticated language and data)

#18 What are your motivations for engaging in such collaborative adaptation processes?

#19 What are your concerns about engaging in such collaborative adaptation processes?

- Complex decision-making
- Time constraints
- Lack of capacities
- Conflicting interests
- Resource constraints
- Other

20 If you wish to elaborate on your answers or add an important element that you feel is missing, please use this space.

Section 4: Personal details

These questions are asked only to track the demographics we have reached with this survey.

#21 What is your age group?

- 18-25
- 26-35
- 36-45
- 46-55
- 56-65
- 66 and over
- I prefer not to answer

#22 What is your gender identity?

- Women
- Man
- Non-binary
- Prefer not to say
- Other

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#23 What's your highest academic degree (High school diploma, Bachelors Degree, Masters Degree, PhD Degree)?

#24 What is your country of residence?

#25 Based on your professional activities, which of the following categories best describes the stakeholder group you belong to?

- Local communities
- Academia and research
- Governments and decision makers
- Civil society representatives
- Citizens
- Investors/economic actors
- Media
- Other

6- Enabling future links with respondents

Way forward

If you would like to be informed of the results of this survey, the outputs or events organised within the AGORA project, please enter your contact details and your preferences in a separate form: <https://forms.office.com/e/Q4KZ4WiJwb>

Your response was submitted.

Thank you for your time and effort in completing this survey. Your answers are of great value to us and will contribute to a better understanding of the current context and to formulate recommendations to support this type of collaborative process for climate change adaptation in the future.

If you would like to be informed of the results of this survey, the outputs or events organised within the AGORA project, please enter your contact details and your preferences in a separate form: <https://forms.office.com/e/Q4KZ4WiJwb>

7- Providing further information

The AGORA project is creating a Digital AGORA - an online platform promoting citizen and stakeholder interaction. It will include a map of citizen engagement initiatives on climate change adaptation. To add an initiative in our database, register it here: <https://www.surveymonkey.com/r/CEImap>

You can also:

- Subscribe to AGORA's Newsletters: <https://adaptationagora.eu/join-our-community/>
- Consult AGORA website: <https://adaptationagora.eu/>

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- Follow us on social media:

Twitter: <https://twitter.com/AgoraAdaptation>

Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/people/Adaptation-AGORA/100090701292038/>

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/adaptation-agora/>

8- Communication and dissemination strategies examples

- **Example of communication for LinkedIn/Facebook:**

 Survey | How to engage people in climate change adaptation? Share your experience with us!

 I seek for your invaluable experience as practitioners, decision-makers and researchers involved in citizen and stakeholder engagement in [#climatechange](#) [#adaptation](#) initiatives.

 The data collected will form the groundwork for identifying key policy priorities to expand and bolster people engagement in adaptation initiatives throughout Europe.

 I invite you to answer this survey (~15min) conducted by the [Adaptation AGORA](#) project:
<https://lnkd.in/ehEG8UNq>

All your experience counts! A huge thank!

- **Example of email**

Dear ...,

The [AGORA project](#), under the EU Mission Adaptation, launched an online survey aiming to assess the supporting factors and the challenges associated with the citizen and stakeholder engagement in climate change adaptation.

We seek for your experience as a (practitioners, decision-makers or researchers) involved in adaptation collaborative initiatives, if it's your case please take 10-15min to fill our survey:

<https://forms.office.com/e/auuxrM2WYF>

The data collected will form the groundwork for identifying key policy priorities to expand and bolster people engagement in adaptation initiatives throughout Europe.

AGORA aims at leveraging and step forwarding best practices, innovative approaches, policy instruments and governance mechanisms to meaningfully and effectively engage communities and regions in climate actions, accelerating and upscaling adaptation process for building a climate resilient Europe.

We would be very grateful if you could complete this survey and share it with your networks.

For further information about the survey or [AGORA project](#), please contact Dr. Enora BRULEY (enora.bruley@unige.ch).

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